

Theory of Age Relativity

Quantifying Time Perception Relative with Age
Jake Fan jake@chaogic.com

ABSTRACT

A mathematical model and the central concept of Time Perception Factor are proposed in an attempt to quantify time perception relative with age.

INTRODUCTION

It's all relative.

When one is young, time crawls. An hour is torturously long, and a year is an eternity. But as one ages, time seems to fly by at an ever increasing rate. Weeks become days, and years feel like months.

*When as a child I laughed and wept, Time crept.
When as a youth I waxed more bold, Time strolled.
When I became a full-grown man, Time ran.
When older still I daily grew, Time flew.
Soon I shall find, in passing on, Time gone.*

– Henry Twells, "Time's Paces" [1]

THEORY

In order to quantify the phenomenon, this paper introduces the **Time Perception Factor - TPF**. In its simplest form, TPF is defined as:

$$TPF = \frac{T}{A} = \frac{D - N}{A} \quad (1.1)$$

where:

- T - a Time interval
- D - a Date in the past, present, or future
- N - the present, Now
- A - one's Age

The Time Perception Factor is inversely proportional to one's age. Or simply, the TPF value represents a number of one's lifetimes. For instance, TPF = 2 represents two lifetimes, and TPF = 0.5 represents half a lifetime.

Time intervals or dates with the same Time Perception Factor feel alike.

To put this in perspective: For quarter a lifetime, 10 years to a 40-year-old feel like 5 years to a 20-year-old, with TPF = 0.25; As of 2012 (N = 2012), a 10-year-old's 9/11 (D = 2001) feels like a 40-year-old's Apollo 11 (D = 1969), with TPF ≈ -1.1.

A few obvious observations immediately follow:

1. The present always has the same Time Perception Factor for everyone regardless of age, with TPF = 0.
2. One's birth date has a constant Time Perception Factor throughout life, with TPF = -1.
3. A date in the past has TPF < 0, while a date in the future has TPF > 0.

~~

TUNING

The simple theoretical model has a few caveats that need to be addressed.

1. Problem at the very young age. A child's brain and its function of time perception are under rapid development. More importantly, memories of such perception are non-existent or sporadic at best for everyone before e.g. age 5, making empirical verification of the model difficult. Therefore, equation (1.1) should have a lower age limit, perhaps arbitrarily with $A \geq 5$ years.
2. Problem at the advanced age. Do an 80-year-old's 10 years really feel like an 8-year-old's 1 year? Conceivably, the effect could attenuate as one gets older and becomes gradually aware at the conscious and subconscious level. A logarithmic age can be introduced for this reason. Modify equation (1.1) with TPF' and A':

$$TPF' = \frac{T}{A'} = \frac{D - N}{A'} \quad (2.1)$$

and:

$$A' = \ln \left(1 + \frac{A}{l} \right)^l \quad (2.2)$$

where:

l - an empirical length of time

$$A' \approx A, \quad \text{if } A \ll l$$

See figure 2 in appendix for an illustration of this modified age A'.

Equation (2.1), however, has its own caveats, mainly: a. One's birth date will no longer have a constant TPF = -1 throughout life; b. A date after one person's birth can have the same TPF value as another, younger person's date before birth.

3. Problem at the very short time scale. A second should obviously feel about the same to everyone regardless of age, since it's roughly the duration of a resting heartbeat. Anything shorter than a second is near or beyond the limit of human perception. The model simply does not concern such a short time scale as seconds or less.

4. Problem at the very long time scale. A time scale significantly longer than the human lifespan and therefore beyond our intuitive comprehension should feel the same to everyone regardless of age. For example 50,000 years should have a TPF value independent of age. To account for this, equation (2.1) can be further modified as:

$$TPF = \frac{TPF'}{\sqrt{1 + \frac{TPF'^2}{C^2}}} \quad (2.3)$$

where:

C - an empirical Constant

$$\lim_{T \rightarrow \infty} TPF = C$$

inversely:

$$TPF' = \frac{TPF}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{TPF^2}{C^2}}}$$

(The physics inclined will notice the above equation's coincidental resemblance to the Lorentz transformation of time dilation in Einstein's Special Theory of Relativity [2].)

Equation (2.3) addresses the problem by converging TPF values at the very long time scale to the upper limit C, but causes all sufficiently long time intervals to have $TPF \approx C$, making them indistinguishable. A simple solution is to make C vary with T for sufficiently large values of T:

$$C = n + \frac{\left(\frac{T}{m}\right)^2}{n + \left|\frac{T}{m}\right|} \quad (2.4)$$

where:

m - a time interval much longer than the human lifespan, arbitrarily defined as a millennium

n - an empirical number, the turning point where TPF starts to become age independent, transitioning from a number of lifetimes to a number of millennia

$$TPF \approx \begin{cases} \frac{T}{A'}, & \text{if } \left| \frac{T}{A'} \right| \ll n \\ \frac{T}{m}, & \text{if } \left| \frac{T}{m} \right| \gg n \end{cases} \quad (2.5)$$

Figure 1. TPF Plots with T between $\pm 1,000, \pm 10,000, \pm 100,000$ Years

CONCLUSION

Following is TPF in its comprehensive form, with l, m, n to be determined empirically:

$$TPF = \frac{T}{\sqrt{\ln^2 \left(1 + \frac{A}{l}\right)^l + \frac{T^2}{\left(n + \frac{\left(\frac{T}{m}\right)^2}{n + \left|\frac{T}{m}\right|}\right)^2}}} \quad (3.1)$$

NOTES

1. When/if in the future we achieve a much longer lifespan than the current ~100 years, the values of l, m, n will need to be adjusted accordingly.
2. The model assumes a normal mental state, i.e. not under physiological, psychological, or emotional influence that would distort all perceptions including time.
3. The phenomenon is by no means unique to time perception. Perceptions of other properties such as light, sound, and unsurprisingly wealth follow the same principle of diminishing returns.

APPENDIX

Figure 2. Modified Age A'

REFERENCES

- [1] H. Twells, *Time's Paces, Hymns and Other Stray Verses*, London: Wells Gardner & Co., p. 34 (1901).
- [2] A. Einstein, *Zur Elektrodynamik bewegter Körper*, *Annalen der Physik* 17, p. 891 (1905).